

PSYCHOSOCIAL FACTORS AND DRUG ABUSE AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN YAKURR LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

By

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates psychosocial factors and drug abuse among adolescents in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the aim of this study, three research questions and three hypotheses were posed to guide the study. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. A sample of two hundred (250) respondents were randomly selected for the study. The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire and stratified and simple random sampling technique was employed to select respondents for the study. For the purpose of data analysis, independent was used to analyzed formulated hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Based on the data collected and analyzed, the result of the analysis revealed that there is a significant influence of age, gender, self-concept of drug abuse among adolescents in the study area. It was recommended that more social workers, human services professionals and educators should be employed in public and private schools for greater sensitization of the public on the dangers of drug usage by adolescents.

Keywords: drug abuse, adolescents, psychosocial factors, age, gender, self-concept.

Introduction

Drug abuse is an emerging global public health issue. The recent drug report-2019 of the United Nation's Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) estimated that 271 million (5.5%) of the global population aged between 15 and 19 years had used drugs in the previous years. The use of drugs can be seen in different dimensions, either for the purpose of health relief or for the purpose of exhibiting abnormal behaviour which triggers or cause psychological changes in the body. Societies in all parts of the world have used drugs that suppress pain and sorrow and also provide pleasurable sensation when consumed to promote the holistic wellbeing (Bernstein, 2018). Some of these drugs that can be used to suppress pain are paracetamol, felvin, panadol, while those illicit drugs used for pleasurable sensation include opiates, stimulants, heroin and so many of them. One of the problems faced by developed nations today, specifically Afghanistan which is seen as the number one on the list of developed countries which has the highest rate of abusing substance like opiate, heroin, marijuana and tobacco that has served as an impetus to violence among youths (Fatoye & Maraking, 2018).

However, drug is a chemical substance that when taken, initiated, absorbed or via a patch on the tongue cause psychological changes in the body. The rate of drug use and misuse in Nigeria among the adolescent age between 13-19 has caused many able bodies especially male and female, who are supposed to study hard for greatness to ending up their lives in psychiatry and other reformatory homes. The adolescents in Nigeria have easy access to substance like cocaine, alcohol, tobacco and even medicines like tramadol. This is also as a result of proliferation of manufacturing industries of these substances, that makes them available. It is on this note, United Nation Office on Drug and Crime (UNODC) world report (2020) revealed that Nigeria top the list of countries in Africa in the use of illicit drugs.

Drug abuse, according to Ajayi and Ayodele (2012), is the wrong use or inappropriate use of chemical substances that are capable of changing functions of cells in the body. Ajayi and Ekundayo (2010) also saw drug abuse as over-dependence and misuse of one particular drug with or without a prior medical diagnosis from qualified health practitioners. According to them, such dangerous drugs include cocaine, Indian hemp (marijuana), morphine, heroin, tobacco, ephedrine, codeine, Valium-five and Chinese capsules as few among the drugs commonly abused by adolescents.

Adolescence is a span of years during which boys and girls move from childhood to adulthood, developing mentally, physically and socially. The seeming upsurge in the use of drugs among adolescents in the study area could be traced to some noticeable factors such as advertisement. The advertising industries have been linking such drugs as tobacco and alcohol intake with athletic prowess, beauty, masculinity, youth success and intellect. Thereby, making it possible for tobacco smoking and drinking of alcohol to be widespread among the adolescents as well as adults who are supposed to be the role models. Similarly, the adolescents see their parents smoke, see their teachers excuse themselves during recess to enjoy cigarette, and also, they see heroes of the movie in the television screen smoke. Besides, the young children are often sent by their parents or guardian to purchase cigarette for them, so they seem to see nothing wrong to use it. In other words, they are irresistibly tempted to follow the examples of their role models and significant others (Oshodi, Aina & Onajoie, 2017).

Substance abuse has created several problems for adolescents. It is the associated problems that make students' flout school rules and regulation, skip classes and get involve in juvenile delinquencies. It has been shown that increase drug abuse among secondary school students is a major contributory factor of ugly confrontations between school authority and students (Blandford, 2000).

Psychosocial factors employed in this study are age, gender, self-concept and attitude. Age is number of years that a person has existed. Young people of adolescents aged 12 to 14 used drugs; they are novelty seekers and excited to satisfy their curiosity. The desire and the courage to experiment new things are much greater in adolescence than in later life. This placed them in high risk behaviour like juvenile delinquencies which increases with age and makes them more prone to substance abuse. The use of cannabis, amphetamines, ecstasy as well as non-medical use of prescription opioids (tramadol, codeine, morphine) and cough syrups containing codeine is common among young people but is negligible in the older population.

Gender is a fact of being male or female. It is believed that certain kind of drug was known to be prevalence in a particular gender, but less significance in the other. Males tend to be involved in risky tendencies like experimenting with drugs, while their counterpart try other

substance of choice. Socially both genders use drugs alike for non-medical purposes such as athletics, beauty enhancement, intellects etc due to general acceptance (Nnana & Runyi, 2024).

Young adults with negative and positive self-concept tend to develop a positive and negative self-concept toward drug use or abuse respectively. However, support of peer and significant few tend to influence the adolescents' self-concept to the positive or negative direction. Drug abuse among adolescents is influenced by positive and negative attitude toward drug use (Nnana & Isaac, 2024). Students' positive attitude against drug abuse is an indication to good behaviour in school setting and society, whereas negative attitude towards drug use may lead to deviant behaviour like tobacco smoking, alcohol drinking, destruction, aggression, stealing, fight and perform poorly in academic etc. Hence, the misuse of drugs can trigger a deviant behaviour in the life of an adolescent. It is against this background that the researcher intends to investigate psychosocial factors and drug abuse among adolescents in Yakurr local government area of Cross River State, Nigeria

Statement of the problem

Drug abuse among adolescents remain part of the major impediments to development in any nation including Nigeria and Yakurr Local Government in particular. There have been many reported cases of drug abuse among adolescents who are leaders of the future. Drug abuse is a major problem that has characterized the enormous crises facing the society today. The critical problem is that in spite of the various measures adopted to prevent drug abuse among adolescents in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State, the incidence of drug abuse has continued to go on the increase. The menace with its associated psychosocial disorder is becoming alarming in recent times. As an anti-social behaviour, it has wrecked and destroyed a lot of adolescents in the society and how I support this claim with studies. It is obvious that most of them indulge in this maladjusted behaviour being ignorant about the inherent dangers in it. The World Health Organization estimated that 70% of premature deaths recorded among adults are due to behavioural tendencies such as smoking of illicit drug which were initiated during adolescence. It was also estimated that about 76.3 million people struggle with alcohol use alone contributing to 1.8 million deaths per year. The United Nations reported that around 185 million people globally over the age of 15 were consuming drugs by the end of the 20th century (UNODC, 2020).

The impact of drug abuse among Nigerian adolescents is reflected in moral bankruptcy, decadence and wasted generation and loss of our societal values and ideas. Others include poor personal hygiene, neuropsychiatric disorders, rape and suicidal tendencies. The situation now appears to be such that no one can claim ignorance of what is happening. There is no doubt that the abuse of substance among adolescents in Yakurr Local Government of Cross River State, Nigeria has continued unabated, thereby creating a social and psychological problem for both users and the society thereby making them a burden to their families and the society.

In Yakurr, Denwigwe, Okpechi, Asuquo and Eze (2018) asserted that substance abuse among young people is a complex and a problematic social phenomenon which is growing steadily worldwide and family influences. most cases drug abuse come with medical, psychiatric, psychological, spiritual, economic, social, family and legal issues and with a significant emotional and economic burden for the affected individuals, their families and society at large.

Drug abuse has become a threat to the lives and success of the adolescents. This is evidently a source of sorrow to the parents, guardians and relatives. It is also a big challenge to the whole nation. The menace can be reduced to the barest minimal, if the adolescents who are known to be the largest consumers are first targeted in their respective post-primary institutions. The government, educational stakeholders, families and other professionals in various disciplines are the key players to proffer solution to this problem ravaging our society. For Instance, every 10th of October, yearly, Nigeria joined other countries worldwide to mark 'International Day against Drug Abuse'; in collaboration with post-primary school authorities, NDLEA, health professionals and other sister agencies to enlighten and educate secondary school students against health hazards of substance abuse. Penalties associated with the use of illicit substances can be harsh, and users in most post-primary institutions are often expelled or rusticated. The medical health care professionals frowned at the uncontrollable ways and manners in which the drugs are sold to the public in our markets and medical stores which are contributory factors to drug abuse. On this note, the selling of all codeine-containing products was banned by the Nigerian government as one of the efforts to address the problem of drug abuse in our society. This was due to severe health outcomes that are visibly suffered by users. (Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency NDLEA, 2019)

The NDLEA has been launching nationwide enforcement activities to seize drug abuse and arrest drug abusers in the community's sensitization program, rehabilitation and border patrol to check-mate illicit drugs to and from Nigeria. The 2019 NDLEA report has shown that in the last 10 years operations, a total of 56,795,555kg of drugs were seized, 85,058 persons with drug related offences were arrested and 16,937 cases were secured and convicted. Recently, the federal government of Nigeria through Pharmacists Council of Nigeria (PCN) an agency in charge of regulating the practice of pharmacy in Nigeria, banned the operation of open drug markets in Nigeria. This effort was introduced to sanitize the drug distribution system in the country. The PCN also prohibits the handling of drugs by unlicensed personnel, especially prescription and controlled of drugs.

It is therefore pertinent to ask: what are the psychosocial factors that influence drug abuse in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State? However, there are related research information regarding psychosocial factors and drug abuse among adolescents: gender, age, attitude and self-concept in Yakurr Local Government Area. The risk factors toward adolescents' substance abuse will give the researcher the ability to utilise counselling strategies to intervene effectively to minimise adolescents' substance abuse. However, certain psychosocial variable that influence substance abuse may vary from one society to another and are influenced by the specific cultural, social and structural features of the society concerned. Therefore, it is imperative to access psychosocial factors that influence drug abuse among adolescents in Yakurr Local government area.

Research questions

The following research questions were formulated in the study

1. To what extent does age influence drug abuse among adolescents?
2. How does gender influence drug abuse among adolescents?
3. To what extent does self-concept influence drug abuse among adolescents?

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to determine psychosocial factors and drug abuse among adolescents in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The specific objectives are:

1. To find out whether there is a significant influence of age on drug abuse among adolescents.
2. To find out whether there is a significant influence of gender on drug abuse among adolescents.
3. To find out whether there is a significant influence of self-concept on drug abuse among adolescents.

Research hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of age on drug abuse among adolescents
2. There is no significant influence of gender on drug abuse among adolescents
3. There is no significant influence of self-concept on drug abuse among adolescents.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was the ex-post facto research design. The area of study is Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Yakurr Local Government was created out of Obubra Local Government in 1987. It is located in the rain forest zone and lies between Latitude 50451N and 50501N, Longitude 80031E and 80081E. It lies within the vegetational belt of southern Nigeria and shares her geographical boundaries with Akamkpa in the West, Biase L.G.A. to the South, Obubra L.G.A. to the North and Abi to the East. The study population comprises of adolescents in Yakurr local government area of Cross River State. This population include male and females. The population of adolescents in the study area is projected at 6,230 senior students in public secondary schools in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The population of this study are SS1 and SS2 students in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. Data used for this study were obtained from both primary and secondary sources.

A sample of 250 respondents was randomly drawn from five (5) schools in the study area, this is for convenience and cost effectiveness. The stratified and simple random sampling techniques were employed in this study. The method of data collection in this study is questionnaire (likert scale questionnaire). The researcher used questionnaire because it is very necessary to get the opinions and reactions of the respondents. The questionnaire was structured in a likert scale, rating from agreed (A), strongly agreed (SA), disagreed (D), strongly disagreed (SD) to elicit information from the respondents on the issue expressed in the questionnaire. The researcher adopted the Independent t-test analysis to give the study independent and dependent variables.

Findings

Data were collected from two hundred (250) respondents. The data was collected in line with the four stated hypotheses based on the sub-variables which were: adolescents' age, gender, self-concept, attitude while the dependent variable is drug abuse. The data were analyzed and presented accordingly as given below:

TABLE 1

General description of data

Variables	N		SD
Age	250	19.2	6.76
Gender	250	28.6	4.01
Self-concept	250	20.2	4.10
Attitude	250	20.2	13.9

Source: Field survey, 2025

Hypothesis one

There is no significant influence of age on drug abuse among adolescents. This hypothesis was analyzed using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The result is presented in table 2. The result in table 2 showed that the calculated f-value of 10.04 was greater than the f-critical of 3.24 at 0.05 levels of significance at 248 degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was rejected and then the findings indicated that there is significant influence of age on adolescents' drug abuse.

TABLE 2

One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of adolescents' age on drug abuse (N=250)

Age	n	\bar{x}	SD
10-12years	34	6.8	3.1
13-15 years	43	8.6	2.19
16-18 years	96	19.2	6.76
Above18 years	77	15.4	2.6
Total	250		

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F-cal	f-critical	p-value
Between group	505	3	168.3			
Within group	268	16	16.75	10.04	3.24	.001
Total	773	19				

Significant at 0.05, f- critical =3.24

Source: Field survey, 2025

Hypothesis two

There is no significant influence of gender on drug abuse among adolescents. This hypothesis was analyzed using independent t-test analysis. The result is presented in table 3. The result in table 3 showed that the calculated t-value of 2.82 was greater than the critical t-value of 1.86 at 0.05 levels of significance at 248 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis was rejected. Then the findings indicated that there is significant influence of gender on students' drug abuse.

TABLE 3

Independent t-test analysis of gender on drug abuse (N=250)

Gender	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-cal	p-value
Male	143		28.6	4.01	248	2.82 0.003
Female	107	21.4	4.25			

Significant at 0.05, df =248, critical t=1.86
Source: Field survey, 2025

Hypothesis three

There is no significant influence of self-concept on drug abuse among adolescents. This hypothesis was analyzed using independent t-test analysis. The result is presented in table 4. The result in table 4 showed that the calculated t-value of 3.83 was greater than the critical t-value of 1.86 at 0.05 level and 248 degrees of freedom. By this result, it implies that adolescents' self-concept significantly influenced the drug abuse. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

TABLE 4

Independent t-test analysis of adolescents' self-concept on drug abuse (N=250)

Adolescents' self-concept	n	x	SD	t-cal	p-value
High	149	29.8	3.96	3.83	0.000
Low	101	20.2	4.10		

Significant at 0.05, df=248, critical t= 1.86
Source: Field survey, 2025

Discussion

Hypothesis one stated that there is no significant influence of age on drug abuse among adolescents. This hypothesis was tested for significance with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Null hypothesis two was rejected meaning that there is significant influence of age on adolescents' drug abuse. Encomium magazine (2013) maintains that adolescents enjoy greater independence; engaged in increased competitive activities which make them prone to engaging in risky behaviours including drug abuse. Hypothesis two stated that there is no significant influence of gender on drug abuse tendency among secondary school students. This hypothesis was tested for significance with independent t-test analysis. Null hypothesis three was rejected meaning that there significantly influence of gender on drug abuse among adolescents. This result is supported by that of Kolip and Schmidt (2019) asserted that male teenagers were perceived to be a 'more-disadvantaged', because of their greater chances of involvement in hazardous health behaviour including drug use; compared to their female counterpart who were usually overlooked because of their less likeness to engage in maladjusted behaviours .

Hypothesis three stated that there is no significant influence of self-concept on drug abuse among adolescents. This hypothesis was tested for significance with independent t-test analysis.

Null hypothesis four was rejected meaning that there is significantly influence of self-concept on drug abuse among adolescents. This result agrees with Bharath & Sreedevi (2016) preposition, that difficult situations can tend to affect adolescent' self-concept in adolescents, thereby making them vulnerable to substance abuse. Many a time's students indulge in drug abuse when tensed by vicissitudes of life because they think that by so doing, it will produce a relaxation effect and decrease in their level of anxiety.

Conclusion

Drug abuse is a global problem that needs a fast and urgent interventions in curbing it. The study revealed that constant use of drugs and the potential of adolescents falling of neck first on the sword of abuse which is highly related or associated with the intense and ill-advised relationship with bad friends or negative peer groups. It was concluded that drug abuse can propel adolescents into deviant behaviour like tobacco smoking, alcohol drinking, destruction, aggression, stealing, fight and poor academic performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

More social workers, human services professionals and educators should be employed in public and private schools for greater sensitization of the public on the dangers of drug usage by adolescents.

Parents should act as educators by influencing their children and wards to shun drug abuse like a plague.

Nigeria Drug Law Enforcement Agency should produce drug abuse counselors and counseling centres in all the state of the federation.

Teachers should try in teaching the students the risks involved in taking drugs and its effects.

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